

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING, THINLAYER CHROATOGRAPHY AND HPTLC STUDIES OF METHANOLIC EXTRACTS OF CITRULLUSLANATUS

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 22/07/2023

Available online

18/08/2023

Keywords

Citrulluslanatus.

Phytochemical screening,

TLC,

HPTLC.

ABSTRACT

Objectives: The present study was carried out to determine the phytochemical constituents, thin layer chromatographic profile and HPTLC Analysis of *Citrullus lanatus* leaf extracts. It has been reportedly used widely in traditional herbal medicine. The leaves of *Citrullus lanatus* analgesic, anti-inflammatory, mosquitocidal, gonorrhea and anti-microbial property. **Materials and methods:** The leaves of *C.lanatus* were collected, dried, pulverized and extracted with methanol using maceration method. The extract was concentrated in vacuo with the aid of rotary evaporator to afford a greenish crude methanol extract (ME). The fractions were subjected to general phytochemical screening and thin-layer chromatography using standard procedures. Quantitative estimation of some secondary metabolites present in the plant using the standard process. The phytochemical evaluation of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* was carried out by using HPTLC studies. **Results:** Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, steroids and triterpenes which varies in other fractions. Thin-layer chromatographic studies using different solvent systems revealed homogenous spots with different Rf values. TLC & HPTLC studies showed the presence of flavonoid, phenolic compound and tannin. In HPTLC studies the extract was compared with standards and the presence of quercetin, gallic acid and catech in were formed. The vitamin B₁ B₂ and vitamin were estimated. **Conclusion:** The results of the study indicated that the leaf of *Citrullus lanatus* contains secondary metabolites and suitable mobile phase for each fraction have been developed.

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Please cite this article in press as **Dr Dhanapal Venkatachalam et al.** Phytochemical Screening, Thinlayer Chroatoigraphy And Hptlc Studies of Methanolic Extracts of *Citrulluslanatus*. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2023;13(08).

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INTRODUCTION

Traditional medicine involved the use of plants, animals and mineral-based medicines to treat and prevent illnesses or maintain well-being¹ According to the World Health Organization WHO, about 80% of the world's population relies on traditional medicine² Most traditional practitioners rely on herbs (plants) which contain some bioactive secondary metabolites including tannins, flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids³ These constituents produce definite physiological action on the human body⁴ *Citrullus lanatus* (Cucurbitaceae) commonly known as watermelon is a prostrate annual plant with several herbaceous firm and stout stems up to 3m long. It produces a fruit that is about 93% water, hence the name "water melon". It is widely distributed in the temperate regions of Africa, central Asia and Mediterranean⁵. It has been cultivated in Africa over 4,000 years⁶. The leaves are a good antimalarial, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, mosquitocidal, and antimicrobial agents and can also be used in the treatment of gonorrhoea (Personal Communication). The present study investigates the qualitative phytochemical screening, quantitative screening and, analyses TLC plates of suitable mobile phase and HPTLC for methanolic extracts from the leaves of *C. lanatus* plant.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and authentication:

Citrullus lanatus was collected from in and around Chembarambakkam, Chennai. India. The plant was identified and authenticated by the taxonomist. The authenticated specimen was deposited in the Department of Pharmacognosy, Sree Sastha Pharmacy College, Chennai. The authentication specimen number is SSPC/P.COG/004/2023. The collected leaves were shade dried, pulverized to get a coarse powder and used for the present study.

Preparation of the Extract

The leaves were shade dried, pulverized, labelled and stored at room temperature. The powdered leaves (154g) were extracted with methanol using maceration method for 3 days. The extract was evaporated in-vacuum using rotary evaporator at 40°C to yield a gummy greenish residue (25.6g) subsequently referred to as the crude methanol extract (ME). Twenty gram (20g) of ME was suspended in distilled water, filtered and partitioned successively into hexane (3.14g, HF), chloroform (0.22g, CF), ethyl acetate (2.43g, EF) and n-butanol (4.40g, BF) fractions respectively. The fractions were concentrated and kept in a refrigerator prior to use

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Portion of the fractions each was subjected to phytochemical screening for the presence of secondary metabolites including, flavonoids, saponins, tannins and steroids/triterpenes and alkaloids using standard procedures⁷⁻⁸

Test for Alkaloids

0.5g of the extract was stirred with 5ml of 1% aqueous hydrochloric acid on a water bath and filtered. 3ml of the filtrate was divided into three. To the first 1ml few drops of freshly prepared Dragendoff's reagent was added. To the second, 1 drop of Meyer's reagent was added. To the third, 1ml of Wagner's reagent was added and observed.

Test for Flavonoids

Ferric chloride test:

To a small portion of the extract, distilled water was added. A drop of ferric chloride was added to a solution of the extract and observed.

NaOH test.

Some portion of the extract was dissolved in 10% aqueous NaOH solution, dilute HCl was added and observed.

Test for Anthraquinones

0.5g of the extract was shaken with 5ml carbon tetrachloride, this was filtered and 10% dilute ammonia solution was added. The mixture was shaken and observed.

Test for Saponins

0.5g of the extract was shaken with distilled water in a test tube. It was allowed to stand for 10 minutes and observed.

Test for Steroids and Triterpenes

Liebermann-Buchard test:

A small portion of the extract was dissolved in chloroform. Equal volume of acetic anhydride and concentrated H₂SO₄ were added down the test tube and observed.

Salkowski test:

A small quantity of the extract was dissolved in 1ml chloroform and to it 1ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added down the test tube and observed.

Test for Tannins**Lead Sub-acetate Test:**

To a small portion of the extract, distilled water was added. 3-5 drops of lead acetate solution was added and observed.

Test for Carbohydrates**Molisch test:**

To a small portion of the extract, distilled water was added and mixed with a few drops of Molisch reagent. 1ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ was carefully added down the side of the inclined tube and observed.

Fehling's Test:

To a small portion of the extract, distilled water was added. 2ml Fehling's solution was added and boiled for 5 minutes and observed.

Test for Phenols

Ferric chloride test: To a small portion of the extract, distilled water was added. A drop of ferric chloride was added to a solution of the extract and observed.

Test for Glycosides**Legal's test:**

To a small portion of the extracts, sodium nitropruside in pyridine and sodium hydroxide was added and observed.

Ferric chloride test:

To a small portion of the extract, distilled water was added. A drop of ferric chloride was added to a solution of the extract and observed.

Estimation of total phenol content⁹⁻¹⁰**Procedure**

Gallic acid was accurately weighed and diluted in water to concentration of 1mg/mL. This solution was suitably diluted to get concentrations ranging from 2, 4, 6, 8, 10µg/ml. 0.5mL of Folin Ciocalteu reagent was added and allowed to stand for 15min. Then 1mL of 10% sodium carbonate solution was added. Finally the mixtures were mixed with distilled water and made upto 10mL, allowed to stand for 30min at room temperature and total phenols were determined by Spectro photometrically at 760nm using the reagent as blank. The methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* was weighed and diluted to get a solution of 1mg/mL. Different concentrations of the solution were taken in separate test tubes. 0.5mL of FolinCiocalteu reagent was added and allowed to stand for 15min. Then 1mL of 10% sodium carbonate solution was added. Finally the mixtures were mixed with distilled water and made upto 10mL, allowed to stand for 30min at room temperature and total phenols were determined by Spectro photometrically at 760nm using the reagent as blank. A calibration curve was generated by plotting concentration of gallic acid versus absorbance. A linear regression equation was determined using regression analysis. The total phenol content was calculated using the linear regression equation and expressed in terms mg of gallic acid equivalent per gm of extract (mg GAE/g). The results obtained are presented in table.

Estimation of total flavonoids content¹¹⁻¹³**Procedure**

An aliquot quantity of quercetin was dissolved in ethanol to get a stock solution of 1mg/mL. Further dilutions were made to get concentrations ranging from 20-100µg/mL. 1mL of the above standard solutions were taken in different volumetric flasks, 0.1mL of aluminum chloride solution, 0.1mL of potassium acetate solution and 2.8mL of ethanol were added and the final volume was then made up to 5mL with distilled water. After 20min the absorbance was measured at 415nm. A sample without aluminium chloride was used as a blank. From the absorbance obtained, a calibration curve was constructed by plotting concentration versus absorbance of quercetin. 1mL of methanolic extract at concentrations 50µg/mL and 100µg/mL were taken and the reaction was carried out as above and the absorbance was measured at 415nm after 20min and the readings were tabulated. The amount of flavonoids present can be determined by linear regression analysis. The total flavonoid content was expressed as mg quercetin equivalents /g of extract.

Estimation of total tannin content¹⁴⁻¹⁵**Procedure**

About 0.2mL of methanolic extract of *C. lanatus* was pipetted into test tubes. To this, 0.5ml of Folin-Denis reagent and 0.8mL of distilled water was added. The tubes were kept aside for 15min. To this, 1mL of sodium carbonate solution was added and the remaining volume was made up with 7.5mL of distilled water. Then the tubes were shaken and the absorbance was recorded at 700nm after 30min. Tannic acid, used as a standard was taken at different concentration i.e 2, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20µg/mL in different test tubes and the procedure adopted above was followed. The calibration curve for tannic acid was plotted using concentration versus absorbance. A linear regression equation was calculated and the equation was used to calculate the amount of total tannins as tannic acid equivalent. The amount of tannin content is expressed in mg/g of extract.

Estimation of vitamins¹⁶⁻²⁰ Estimation of vitamin B₁²¹⁻²⁴

Procedure

Thiamine was weighed and dissolved in water to get stock solution of 2mg/mL. Further dilutions were made to get the concentrations ranging from 100-500µg/mL. To 10mL of sample, 10mL of potassium dichromate solution was added and the colour produced was measured at 360nm. A calibration curve was constructed by plotting concentration versus absorbance of thiamine (Fig.12). The above procedure was repeated for the plant extract and the absorbance was measured at 360nm and the readings were tabulated in Table 9. The amount of vitamin B₁ present can be determined by linear regression analysis. The vitamin B₁ content was expressed as mg/g of extract.

Estimation of vitamin B₂

Procedure

Riboflavin was weighed and dissolved in water to get stock solution of 20mg/mL. Further dilutions were made to get the concentrations ranging from 2-10mg/mL. To 15mL of sample and 10mL of 0.5% potassium permanganate and 1mL of 30% hydrogen peroxide were added and allowed to stand over a hot water bath for about 30min. 2mL of 40% sodium sulphate was added. This was made up to 5mL. The absorbance of the chromogen was measured at 550nm in a UV visible spectrophotometer. A calibration curve was constructed by plotting concentration versus absorbance of riboflavin. The above procedure was repeated for the plant extract and the absorbance was measured at 550nm and the readings were tabulated in Table 10. The amount of vitamin B₂ present can be determined by linear regression analysis. The vitamin B₁ content was expressed as mg/g of extract.

Estimation of vitamin C²⁵⁻²⁶

Procedure

Ascorbic acid was weighed and dissolved in water to get stock solution of 1mg/mL. Further dilutions were made to get the concentrations ranging from 40-200µg/mL. To 1mL of sample 0.5mL of di nitro phenyl hydrazine solution was added and incubated for 3h at 37°C. After 3h, 2.5mL of 85% sulphuric acid was added and the absorbance was measured after 30min at 520nm. A calibration curve was constructed by plotting concentration versus absorbance of ascorbic acid (Fig.14). The procedure was repeated for the plant extract as above and the absorbance was measured at 520nm after 3h and the readings were tabulated in Table 11. The amount of vitamin C present can be determined by linear regression analysis. The vitamin C content was expressed as mg/g of extract.

THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY²⁷

Preparation of TLC Plates

The adsorbent (silica gel G) slurry was prepared in water in the ratio of (1: 2). The glass plates (20cm x 5cm) were cleaned and laid in a row as a template, the suspension was poured into Stahl TLC spreader, which was adjusted to 0.25mm thickness and coated in a single passage of the spreader over them. These plates were air dried and activated in hot air oven at 105°C for 30min and kept in a dessicator. The plates were used as the stationary phase or Pre-coated aluminum plates coated with silica gel G F₂₅₄ (Merck) were also used for analysis.

Sample application

The extracts were dissolved in mobile phase and the spot was applied on the TLC plates using capillary tube.

Development of the chromatogram

After drying of the spot, the plates were developed in a chromatographic tank containing the solvent system. After one third of the plate was developed the plates were taken outside and dried. The TLC plate was examined visually or under UV light.

Solvent system I

Stationary phase-Silica gel G

Mobile phase -Toluene: Ethyl Acetate: Methanol(7:2:1)

Detecting agent -visual & UV light

Solvent system II

Stationary phase-Silica gel G

Mobile phase-Chloroform: Methanol(9.5:1) Detecting agent- visual & UV light

The R_f values were calculated using the formula [Distance travelled by solute/ Distance travelled by solvent]. The phytochemical evaluation of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* was carried out by using TLC studies.

HIGH PERFORMANCE THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY

The phytochemical evaluation of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* was carried out by using HPTLC studies.

Instrument used

CAMAG TLC Scanner 3 "Scanner3-070408"S/N 070408(1.41.21) was used for detection and CAMAGL inomat 5 sample applicator was used for the application of the track. Twin trough plate development chamber was used for development of chromatogram. Software used was win CATS 1.4.3

Sample

The Methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* was dissolved in mobile phase and 2 μ l sample is applied as 8mm band was used for taking HPTLC fingerprint.

Stationary Phase

HPTLC plates silica gel 60F254

Mobile phase

Toluene: ethyl acetate: methanol (7: 2: 1) was used as the mobile phase for development of chromatogram. The mobile phase was taken in a CAMAG twin trough glass chamber.

Detection wave length

The developed plates were examined at wavelength 254 and 366nm and @520nm in Densitometry TLC Scanner 3. The TLC visualization, 3D display of the finger print profile and peak display at 254 and 366nm are presented.

RESULTS

Percentage Yield The percentage yield of each fraction is shown in (Table 1). Crude methanol extract (25.6g), hexane fraction (3.14g), chloroform fraction (0.22g), ethyl acetate fraction (2.43g) and n-butanol fraction (4.40g).

Phytochemical Screening

The general preliminary phytochemical screening conducted on the fractions revealed the presence of various secondary metabolites as shown in (Table 2).

Table 1: Percentage Yield of Extract.

S.NO	FRACTION	COLOUR OF EXTRACT	YIELD OF EXTRACT(gm)	YIELD OF EXTRACT %
1	Hexane	Green	3.14	15.70
2	Chloroform	Yellow green	0.22	1.10
3	Ethyl acetate	Brown	2.34	12.15
4	n-Butanol	Brown	4.40	22.00
5	Methanol	Green	25.60	16.62

$$\% \text{ Yield} = \frac{\text{Final weight of extract}}{\text{Initial weight of extract}} \times 100$$

Table 2: Phytochemical Constituents of Methanolic Leaf Extract of *Citrullus lanatus*.

Constituents	Test	Observation	Inference				
			ME	HF	CF	EF	BF
Saponins	Frothing	Frothing persist for 15mins	÷	÷	÷	=	-
Alkaloids	Mayer's	White cream ppt	÷	-	÷	÷	-
	Draggondorf's	Orange ppt	÷	-	÷	-	-
	Wagner's	Reddish Brown ppt	÷	-	÷	÷	-
Flavonoids	FeCl ₃	Green or violet ppt	+	-	-	+	+
	Shinoda	Orange-red ppt	÷	-	÷	÷	-
Tannins	Lead sub-acetate	Cream ppt	÷	-	-	÷	÷
Steroids & Terpenes	Lieberman Buchard Salkowski	Blue-green color at interphase Reddish color	÷	÷	÷	-	-
Anthraquinones	Borntragers	Pink or violet	-	-	-	-	-
Carbohydrates	Molisch's	Violet ring	÷	÷	÷	-	-
	Fehling's	Red	÷	÷	-	-	-
Phenols	FeCl ₂	Bluish black color	÷	-	-	÷	÷
Glycosides	Legal's	Pink-blood red ppt	÷	-	-	÷	÷
	Fehling's	Red ppt	÷	-	-	÷	÷

Estimation of total phenols

The results for the total phenolestimation of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* are tabulated in Table 3 and Fig.1

Table3: Total phenolic content in methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* in terms of gallic acid equivalents.

S.No.	Conc. of gallic acid in $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Absorbance at 760nm	Conc. of extract in $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Abs at 760nm*	Amount of total phenolic content in terms mgGAE/g of extract*
1	2	0.229 ± 0.010	50	0.256 ± 0.004	43.90 ± 0.304
2	4	0.452 ± 0.006	100	0.578 ± 0.004	50.20 ± 0.373
3	6	0.695 ± 0.005			
4	8	0.918 ± 0.031			
5	10	1.162 ± 0.028		Average	47.05 ± 0.338

*Mean of three readings \pm SEM

Estimation of total flavonoids

The results for the total flavonoid estimation of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* are tabulated in Table 4. and Fig 2

Table4: Total flavonoid content per gram of extract in terms of Quercetin by aluminium chloride method.

S. No.	Concentration of quercetin in $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Absorbance at 415nm	Conc. of methanolic extract in $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Absorbance at 415nm	Amount of total flavonoid content in terms mg quercetin equivalent/ g of extract
1	20	0.589 ± 0.01	50	0.090 ± 0.001	86.55 ± 0.21
2	40	1.151 ± 0.04	100	0.243 ± 0.003	93.44 ± 0.39
3	60	1.710 ± 0.09			
4	80	2.390 ± 0.03			
5	100	3.112 ± 0.03		Average	89.99 ± 0.30

*Mean of three readings \pm SEM

Total tannin estimation

The results for the total tannin estimation of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* are tabulated in Table 5 & Fig 3

Table5: Total tannin content in ethanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* in terms of tannic acid equivalents.

S.No.	Conc. of tannic acid in $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Absorbance at 760nm	Conc. of methanolic extract in $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Absorbance at 760nm*	Amount of total tannin content in terms mg tannic acid/g of extract*
1	4	0.098 ± 0.020	10	0.060 ± 0.03	260.60 ± 1.51
2	8	0.183 ± 0.010	20	0.131 ± 0.07	292.42 ± 2.00
3	12	0.203 ± 0.010			
4	16	0.361 ± 0.200			
5	20	0.451 ± 0.100		Average	276.51 ± 1.75

*Mean of three readings \pm SEM

VitamicB₁ Content

The results for vitamin B₁ content of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* are presented in Table 6.

Table6: Estimation of Vitamin B₁ in *Citrullus lanatus*.

S. No.	Conc. of Thiamine in $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Absorbance at 360nm	Conc. of methanolic extract in $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Absorbance at 360nm	Amount of vitamin B ₁ present mg/g of extract
1	100	0.168 ± 0.001	100	0.286 ± 0.004	54.82 ± 0.006
2	200	0.367 ± 0.002	200	0.321 ± 0.007	55.02 ± 0.006
3	300	0.656 ± 0.002	300	0.456 ± 0.003	59.00 ± 0.002
4	400	0.856 ± 0.001		Average	56.28 ± 0.004
5	500	1.172 ± 0.003			

*Mean of three readings \pm SEM

VitamicB₂ Content

The results for vitamin B₂ content of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* are presented in Table 7.

Table7: Estimation of Vitamin B₂ in *Citrullus lanatus*.

S.No.	Conc. of Riboflavin in mg/mL	Absorbance 360nm	at Conc. of methanolic ext. in mg/mL	Absorbance 360nm	at Amount of vitamin B ₂ present/mg/g of extract
1	2	0.161 ± 0.006	2	0.047 ± 0.004	31.99 ± 0.011
2	4	0.377 ± 0.012	4	0.111 ± 0.007	32.50 ± 0.006
3	6	0.555 ± 0.002	6	0.203 ± 0.003	37.29 ± 0.010
4	8	0.766 ± 0.005			
5	10	0.958 ± 0.004			
				Average	34.00 ± 0.009

*Mean of three readings± SEM

Vitamin C Content

The

Results for vitamin C content of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* are presented in **Table 8****Table8: Estimation of Vitamin C in *Citrullus lanatus*.**

S.No.	Conc. of ascorbic acid in µg/mL	Absorbance 520nm	at Conc. of methanolic ext in µg/mL	Absorbance 520nm	at Amount of vitamin C present/g of extract
1	40	0.135 ± 0.000	100	0.076 ± 0.004	237.03 ± 0.006
2	80	0.265 ± 0.015	200	0.137 ± 0.007	253.70 ± 0.006
3	120	0.346 ± 0.010			
4	160	0.468 ± 0.011			
5	200	0.525 ± 0.010			
				Average	245.37 ± 0.006

*Mean of three readings± SEM

THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHYThe number of spots, R_f value of the same and the colour of the spots under UV light 366nm and visible light is presented in **Table 9****Table 9: Phytochemical evaluation of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* by TLC studies.**

S.No	Solvent system	Detecting agent	No. of spots	Colour of spots	R _f values
1.	Toluene: Ethyl acetate Methanol (7 : 2 :1)	Under UV at 366nm	5	Orange	0.94
				Dark orange	0.84
				Dark red	0.72
				Light pink	0.45
				Light pink	0.37
		Under Visible light	6	Yellow	0.92
				Brown	0.82
				Dark green	0.72
				Yellowish green	0.58
				Yellowish green	0.47
2	Chloroform: Methanol (9.5 : 1)	Under UV at 366nm	4	Dark brown	0.90
				Dark orange	0.72
				Yellow	0.68
				Light pink	0.46
		Under Visible light	6	Dark green	0.92
				Yellow	0.74
				Yellow	0.70
				Light green	0.52
				Brown	0.46
				Brown	0.34

The extract showed 5 spots at 366nm and 6 spots at visible light. The R_f value of 0.72, 0.37 and 0.45 may be due to the presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds and tannin. When viewed under UV at 366nm and visible light after development in the mobile phase namely chloroform: methanol (9.5:1). The R_f value of 0.9 and 0.72 may be due to the presence of Cucurbitacin glucoside B and Cucurbitacin glucoside E. The extract also showed different R_f value under UV at 366nm and Visible light. The R_f may be due to the presence of different active principle might be responsible for the therapeutic activity.

Mobile phase- Toluene:Ethyl acetate:Methanol(7:2:1)

Fig.7:T.L.C analysis of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* @366nm and Visible light.

Mobile Phase: Chloroform :Methanol (9.5 : 1)

Fig.8:TLC analysis of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* @366nm and Visible light.

HIGH PERFORMANCE THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY

The visualization of the HPTLC plate of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* at 254nm and 366nm is presented in Fig 9. The photo of plate at 254nm showed the presence of 8 spots while at 366nm showed the presence 8 spots.

The 3D display of the fingerprint profile and the peak display of methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* at 254nm and 366nm is presented in Figs 18. The display at 254nm shows the presence of 8 peaks while at 366nm shows the presence 8 peaks. The R_f values of the peaks along with the area under the curve for each peak at 254 and 366 nm are tabulated in Table 10.

Table13: R_f value of the spots and their area under curve at 254 and 366nm.

S. No	R_f Value @ 254nm				AREA(AU) @ 254nm			
	TRACK				TRACK			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
1	0.38	0.46	0.71	0.15	9798.0	27344.1	1187.6	248.6
2				0.18				156.4
3				0.36				1320.9
4				0.45				17028.3
5				0.65				1513.1
6				0.72				326.7
7				0.77				291.7
8				0.84				2203.4

S.No	@366nm	
	R _f Value	AREA(AU)
	1	2
1	0.15	758.8
2	0.18	135.7
3	0.39	1647.0
4	0.50	1881.2
5	0.65	9744.8
6	0.72	941.5
7	0.80	348.2
8	0.85	2984.6

The HPTLC finger print profile of the methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* R_f values compared with standard quercetin, gallic acid and catechin. The methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* R_f values also coincided with standard R_f values and hence it may be confirmed that the methanolic extract showed the presence of quercetin, gallic acid and catechin.

Fig.9: Visualization of TLC plate.

Fig.10: Peak Display

Track1: Catechin, Track2: Gallic acid,

Track3: Quercetin, Track 4: Methanolic extract of *Citrullus lantus* leaf.

Track-3

Track-4

@366nm Extract.

DISCUSSION

The result of preliminary phytochemical screening of the crude methanol extract revealed the presence of all the constituents tested including; alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, carbohydrates, phenols, glycosides, except anthraquinones which varies in the fractions. Hexane fraction revealed the presence of saponins, steroids, terpenes carbohydrates and chloroform fraction revealed the presence of saponins, steroids and terpenes. Ethylacetate fraction indicated the presence of all the constituents tested except for saponins, steroids, terpenes, carbohydrates, anthraquinones and carbohydrates and n-butanol fraction revealed the presence of all the constituents except steroids, terpenes and carbohydrates.

These constituents are responsible for most pharmacological activities of plants²⁸⁻²⁹ Phytochemical constituents give different R_f values in different solvent system. This variation in R_f values provides a very important clue in understanding of their polarity and also helps in selection of appropriate solvent system for separation of pure compounds incorporated in different fractions by column chromatography. Mixture of solvents with variable polarity in different ratio can be used for separation of pure compound from plant extract. The selection of appropriate solvent system for a particular plant extract can only be achieved by analysing the R_f values of compounds in different solvent system [8, 9]. Thin-layer chromatographic analysis carried out on all the fractions revealed homogenous spots which is not the case using some solvent systems. The extract showed 5 spots at 366nm and 6 spots at visible light. The R_f value of 0.72, 0.37 and 0.45 may be due to the presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds and tannin. When viewed under UV at 366nm and visible light after development in the mobile phase namely chloroform: methanol (9.5:1). The R_f value of 0.9 and 0.72 may be due to the presence of Cucurbitacin glucoside B and Cucurbitacin glucoside E. The extract also showed different R_f value under UV at 366nm and Visible light. The R_f may be due to the presence of different active principle might be responsible for the therapeutic activity. The HPTLC finger print profile of the methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* R_f values compared with standard quercetin, gallic acid and catechin. The methanolic extract of *Citrullus lanatus* R_f values also coincided with standard R_f values and hence it may be confirmed that the methanolic extract showed the presence of quercetin, gallic acid and catechin.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the leaf of *Citrullus lanatus* contains secondary metabolites that can be used in traditional medicine to treat ailments. Further detailed isolation and characterization of active constituents of *Citrullus lanatus* is on-going.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author was thankful to the Chairman of Sree Sastha Pharmacy College, Chennai-Bangalore Highway, Chembarambakkam, Chennai, Tamilnadu for providing facilities to carry out the present research work.

Competing interests

Author has declared that no competing interests exist

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